

THE MOST IMPORTANT FEATURES OF TRANSLATING FOREIGN LANGUAGES INTO UZBEK

N.M. Toshpulatova

Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Pedagogical Mastery
Center of Fergana Region Department of Teaching Technologies on Pedagogy and Psychology
Lecturer of the Course "Professional Development of the Educator and Collaboration"
(FarSUResearcher)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14846530>

Abstract. *This article discusses about translated works.*

Keywords: *translation, translator, century, nation, world, language.*

Starting from the second half of the 19 th century, the translation work from Russian to Uzbek began to develop. Efforts to translate poetic works written in Uzbek into Russian commenced. In Russian translation studies, significant work has been done in accordance with practical activities in this field. The textbook "Fundamentals of General Translation Theory" by A.V. Fyodorov, along with the works of scholars such as Yu.M. Katser, V.A. Kunin, Ya.I. Resker, V.N. Komissarov, L.S. Barkhudarov, V.N. Krupnov, R.K. Minyar-Beloruhev, S.S. Tolstoy, M.M. Morozov, A.D. Shveyser, and others, is based on the extensive experience gained from translations carried out from Western European languages into Russian. There are works dedicated to the issue of translation education. M.N.D. Cheburashkin's book "Technical Translation in School" is intended for students of grades IX-X in schools where English is taught (Moscow, "Prosveshchenie" publishing house, 1972). In Georgia, G.R. Gachechiladze's work "Introduction to the Theory of Artistic Translation" (Tbilisi, 1970) is well-known. Jumaniyoz Sharipov's "On the History of Translation in Uzbekistan" (Tashkent, 1965), Azerbaijani Bayram Khorunogli Tohirbayev's "Philosophical Problems of the Science of Translation" (Baku, 1974), and Belarusian P.I. Koianev's "Issues of the History and Theory of Artistic Translation" (Minsk, 1972) serve as important resources for clarifying the theoretical aspects of translation (type, concept, phenomenon, viewpoint). The rich experience gained in Russian translation studies and in the other republics serves as a school for us. Each republic has its own unique aspects of translation education.

In the Russian school of translation, translation education has taken on a traditional form. The education in Russian translation studies is based on the practice of translating from English, German, and French into Russian and from Russian into Western languages. About 60% of the general translation products into Uzbek consist of books translated from Russian. Works of Western European literature have also been translated into Uzbek from Russian. Significant scholarly thought in the field of translation theory developed in the second half of the 20th century. During this period, the theoretical problems of translation began to be addressed abroad. John Catford's lectures in Edinburgh and his monograph "Linguistic Theory of Translation" (London, 1965), along with George Mounin's works "Theoretical Problems of Translation" published based on his doctoral dissertation in French (Paris, 1963) and Italian (Turin, 1965), are considered achievements in this field.

In 1969, Eugene Nida and Charles Taber published a book titled "The Theory and Practice of Translation" in London. It presented theoretical conclusions derived from applying linguistics to translation and exploring its potential uses. Translation theory was developed in England, France, Germany, and Western European countries.

In German, Julius Wirl's monograph on translation issues was published in Austria (Vienna, 1958); Wilhelm Wilmann's book on harmony and inconsistencies in translation appeared in Germany (Cologne, 1959), along with Rudolf Yumpelt's foundational work on the translation of scientific and technical literature (Berlin, 1961) and a collection titled "The Art of Translation" prepared by the Academy of Fine Arts (Munich, 1962). In Switzerland, Fried's book was published (Zurich, 1963). Scientific research on translation studies surged in the Commonwealth countries of Europe. In Germany, Harold Raab and Otto Braun's collection "Introduction to Translation Theory" was published (Berlin, 1959); Otto Kaden's study "Chance and Regularity in Translation" (Leipzig, 1968); Joseph Kardosh's "Problems of Artistic Translation" (Budapest, 1965), Emil Sabok's "Artistic Translation" (Budapest, 1961), and Lyubomir Ognyanov Rizov's "Fundamentals of the Art of Translation" (Sofia, 1955) were notable contributions.

In Poland, O. Voytasevich's "Introduction to Translation Theory" was released (Wrocław-Warsaw, 1957); in Czechoslovakia, JiříLevý's "The Art of Translation" (Prague, 1963); and in Yugoslavia, the collection "Fundamentals of Translation Theory" (Belgrade, 1963) was published.

Eugene Nida's book "On Translation Studies" (Leiden, 1964) provided an overview of theoretical concepts. This overview is reflected in the works of Edmon Cary's "Translation in Modern Times" (Geneva, 1956) and Theodor Severin's "The Art of Translation" (London, 1957). Translation issues are also being researched in America.

In the United States, a collection of articles titled "On Translation" was published (Cambridge-Massachusetts, 1959; New York, 1966). In 1961, the Center for Translation Studies in Austin prepared the "Texas Collection," dedicated to the foundations of translation studies. In Uruguay, Olaf Bliksen published "Artistic Translation and Its Problems" (Montevideo, 1954), and in Brazil, Basilio Silveira's "The Art of Translation" (São Paulo, 1954; 2nd edition, 1956) and Paulo Ronai's "Translation Skills" (Rio de Janeiro, 1956) gained recognition.

The International Federation of Translators held congresses in various locations: in Warsaw (Poland) in 1958, in Bad Godesberg (Germany) in July 1959, in Dubrovnik (Yugoslavia) in August-September 1963, and in Lahti (Finland) in August 1966. In October 1977, an international symposium for translators took place in Moscow.

The International Federation of Translators (FIT) publishes the central journal "Babylon" in Bonn (Berlin) and the "Journal of Translators" in Montreal (Canada), as well as "Linguist" in Brussels (Belgium) and "Translator" in Geneva (Switzerland). In Cambridge (USA), a collection titled "Automatic Translation" was released, along with the monthly bulletin "Translator" published in Stuttgart and Frankfurt am Main (Germany), where theoretical articles on translation theory have been featured.

Significant work has been done in translation activities and translation theory. From the early years of Russian translation studies, M. Gorky led the scientific exploration in this field. The starting point for this activity was K. I. Chukovsky's book "Principles of Artistic Translation." K. I. Chukovsky continued this effort in collaboration with A. V. Fyodorov in their book "The Art of Translation" (Leningrad, 1939).

The book reflected two branches of the theoretical study of translation issues that existed in the 1930s: K. I. Chukovsky, with his work "Principles of Artistic Translation" (published in 1936-41 and 1964), focused on literary studies, while A.V. Fyodorov highlighted linguistic and stylistic aspects in his textbook "Introduction to Translation Theory" (published in 1941, 1953, 1958, and 1968). During the 1930s and 40s, various authors published their research. Notable works include M. P. Aleskeyev's "Problems of Artistic Translation" (Irkutsk, 1931), D. S. Usov's "Basic Principles of Translation Work" (Moscow, 1934), and G. P. Serdyuchenko's "Essays on Translation Issues" (Nalchik, 1948).

In the 1950s and 60s, interesting collections related to translation were published by the Union of Soviet Writers, including "Problems of Artistic Translation" (1955) and "Translation Skills" (1959-75, 1977). The regular collection "Translator's Notebooks," edited by L. S. Barkhudarov, published by the "International Relations" publishing house, addressed translation and linguistic issues.

Monographs on translation studies emerged: in 1973, two works were published: V. N. Komissarov's "A Word About Translation" and A. D. Shveyser's "Translation and Linguistics" (Voenizdat). In 1975, L. S. Barkhudarov's "Language and Translation" was released, followed by V. N. Krupnov's "In the Creative Laboratory of the Translator", T. R. Leviskaya and A. Fiterman's "Translation Issues," and L. A. Chernyakhovskaya's "Translation and Meaning Structure" in 1976.

Translation issues were discussed at the meetings and gatherings of the Writers' Union during the 1950s to 70s, including the II Congress of Soviet Writers in December 1954, where the stenograms of presentations by P. Antokolskiy, M. Avezov, and M. Ril'skiy were recorded.

In December 1954, the Conference of Translators of the Literatures of the Peoples of the USSR was held in Moscow, followed by an extended meeting of the Secretariat of the Union of Writers in October 1960, dedicated to translation issues. In the summer of 1970, the All-Union Meeting of Writer-Translators took place, and in 1978, an international symposium for translators was organized.

In Almaty in 1960, an inter-republican council was established for translating from Russian into the languages of the peoples of Central Asia, Kazakhstan, and Azerbaijan. In 1961, a regional meeting on artistic literature translation was held in Kyrgyzstan, followed by an All-Russian meeting in Qozan in 1962, and a regional gathering of translators in Tbilisi in the same year. In Baku in 1967, a special congress of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union occurred, and significant sources from major gatherings were published in Ulan-Ude.

In Leningrad, "Translation Theory and Criticism" (1962) was published, and in Moscow, two volumes titled "Current Problems of the Theory of Artistic Translation" (1967) and "Translation Theory and Teaching Methodology Issues" (1970) were released. Steps were taken to create a history of translation in Russia, resulting in the publication of "Russian Writers on Translation: XVIII-XX Centuries" (1960).

In Leningrad, theoretical studies addressing literary-aesthetic issues emerged, while in Moscow, research written within the framework of structural linguistics was produced. In Kyiv in 1958, M. Ril'skiy's work "Artistic Translation from One Slavic Language into Russian" was published in Russian, and a collection of articles on language and translation issues by O. Kundzich appeared in Ukrainian (the work was expanded and published in Russian in 1973 under the title "Word and Image"). G. R. Gachschiladze's monograph "Realistic Translation Issues" was published in Tbilisi in 1959 (in Georgian) and in 1964 (in Russian).

The theoretical study of translation strengthened in the cities of the USSR. In 1955, Jumshud Azimov's "Principles of Translation" was published in Azerbaijan in Baku; in 1962, S. Taljonov's "Main Problems of Artistic Translation" was published in Kazakhstan; in 1965, Levon Mirtchyan's "Poems and Translations" was released in Yerevan; and in 1978, a collection of articles titled "Beloved and Cherished" was published in Moscow.

At the end of the 18th century and the beginning of the 19th century, among Tatar intellectuals, those who knew Russian made up a significant majority compared to the remote regions of Russia (Turkestan). Numerous articles dedicated to teaching and learning Russian appeared in newspapers and journals, and there were enough poets and writers translating works from Russian literature.

In 1905, the translation of Russian artistic literature into Tatar began to flourish. New newspapers, journals, and established publishing houses published works by representatives of classical Russian literature such as Zhukovsky, Pushkin, Gogol, Lermontov, Goncharov, Chekhov, Pisarev, and Gorky in Tatar translations, in the form of books or articles. These translated works were distributed in Baku, Ashgabat, Khorezm, and Bukhara.

Talented Tatar poets and writers like Abdulla Tokay, Majid Gafuriy, Fotih Karimiy, S. Sunchalay, and A. Battollar enriched Tatar literature by translating remarkable works of Russian writers. Poet Majid Gafuriy translated I. A. Krylov's fables, while A. Tokay translated poems by Pushkin, M. Yu. Lermontov, and other classical Russian poets. The great figure of Russian literature, Tolstoy, had his works translated into Tatar, allowing the Tatar people to read them in their native language. The translated works of Tolstoy spread throughout Tataristan, Central Asia, and Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, due to the long-standing tradition of translating books from foreign languages into Uzbek, this field has a rich heritage, abundant resources, and countless opportunities.

REFERENCES

1. Ochilov. E, Tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyoti. –T., 2012 .
2. Salomov G'. Tarjimon mahorati. Toshkent: "Fan", 1979.
3. Salomov G'. Tilva tarjima. Toshkent: "Fan", 1960-66. 244-bet
4. Salomov G'. Tarjima san'ati. Toshkent: G'. G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1973.